

WCRO-2025-01424

Details

Working Title High Seas Tuna Purse Seine
Request Received May 9, 2025

Region WCRO
Division Protected Resources Division (PRD)
Branch Long Beach

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
Fishery	MSA Action-Fishing Gear Impacts

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Commerce (DOC) - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) - Office of Sustainable Fisheries, Domestic Fisheries Division

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Fish	Giant Manta Ray	<i>Manta birostris</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Eastern Pacific DPS	Endangered Eastern Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Pinniped	Guadalupe Fur Seal	<i>Arctocephalus townsendi</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	East Pacific DPS	Threatened East Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	North Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered North Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened All Other Areas	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	Mexico's Pacific Coast Breeding Colonies	Endangered Mexico's Pacific Coast Breeding Colonies	✗	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Central America DPS	Endangered Central America DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Mexico DPS	Threatened Mexico DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗

Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	X	X
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Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Mexico DPS	Designated Mexico DPS
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Central America DPS	Designated Central America DPS

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
No location details available						

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
No GIS details available									